

Women in Teaching Profession: Impacts and Challenges

Authors : A. M. Sultana, Norhirdawati Binti Mhd Zahir, Norzalan Hadi Yaacob

Abstract : Recently in Malaysia, women's participation in teaching profession has increased. The increasing trend of women's participation in the teaching profession poses challenges in families, especially in the developing countries like Malaysia. One of these challenges, concerns in balancing their role between family and job responsibility that faced by many women teachers. The purpose of this study is to discover how women teachers' impact on family happiness and the challenges faced by them in balancing their role between family and job responsibility. The findings presented in this study are based on survey research in a secondary school Dato' Bijaya Setia in the district of Gugusan Manjoi which is located in Kedah, Malaysia. The study found that employment of women in economic activity has several beneficial impacts of improving the economic condition of the family. The results also revealed that in low income earning families, both husbands and wives' employment contribute to the family income that less likely to experience of family poverty. The study also showed despite women's teachers' significant role towards the overall development of the family, the majority of women teachers encountered a number of difficulties in balancing their role between family and job responsibility especially when they need to work more than the normal working time. Therefore, it is common for the majority of women suffering from psychological stress when they are unable to complete the task at a fixed time. The present study also suggests implication of family friendly policy and its appropriate practice to support the women teachers who are significantly contributing to family, community and the country.

Keywords : emotional exhaustion, family friendly policy, work family conflict, women teacher

Conference Title : ICWMS 2014 : International Conference on Women, Media and Sexuality

Conference Location : Toronto, Canada

Conference Dates : June 16-17, 2014